

Analysis and measurement of thermally induced mean stresses
in a metal matrix composite

B. Johannesson* and S.L. Ogin

Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Surrey,
Guildford, Surrey, GU2 5XH, England

*Current address: Materials Department, Risø National Laboratory,
DK-4000 Roskilde, Denmark

Abstract

Thermally induced mean stresses in a planar random, alumina fibre reinforced aluminium composite are studied in monotonic and cyclic Bauschinger experiments at room temperature and -196°C (77 K) for composites with a range of fibre volume fractions (0% to 23%). A method of analysing the results of the Bauschinger experiments is used which allows for a separation of thermally and plastically induced mean stresses and enables a comparison of the thermal stress derived from Bauschinger experiments and monotonic tests to be made. It is shown that, at least for small cumulative plastic strains and small plastic strain amplitudes, the reduction in the thermal stress with cycling, which is typical of these composites, is not caused by irreversible damage.

Keywords: Planar random fibre reinforced aluminium composites, cyclic Bauschinger experiments, internal stresses.

1. Introduction

Thermally and plastically induced mean stresses in metal matrix composites have been studied extensively by a number of authors [1-8]. Experimental information on these stresses has been obtained mainly by mechanical testing, X-ray or neutron diffraction [2,5,8-10]. The method primarily used to estimate the magnitude of the thermal stress is to compare flow curves in tension and compression [11]. Another method, based on the analysis of cyclic Bauschinger experiments, was introduced in [12].

In a Bauschinger experiment, the permanent softening, $\Delta\sigma$, is often measured so that comparisons can be made with theories on the mean stress hardening rate [2,5,8]. The permanent softening gives information on both the thermally and plastically induced mean stresses and, provided that the thermal stress does not change in the course of cycling [5], the mean stress hardening rate is readily derived from these experiments - or the thermal stress, if required. However, in planar random fibre reinforced aluminium composites, the thermal

stress is not constant but decreases with cycling [12]. In view of this, a simple extension of the way in which cyclic Bauschinger experiments are analysed was proposed in [12] which enables a separation of the thermal and mean stresses to be made. The purpose of this paper is to include composites with a wide range of fibre volume fractions and measurements of the thermal stresses at both room temperature and 77 K (analysis of the mean stress hardening rates for these composites will be published elsewhere). Further, the stress separation technique for the cyclic Bauschinger experiments produces values of the thermal stress in the composites which can be compared with results obtained from monotonic tests.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. Materials and specimen preparation

Pure aluminium (99.98% Al) was chosen for the matrix of the composites to avoid complications due, for example, to precipitates and dispersions. Saffil RF grade alumina fibres from ICI were used as reinforcement [13]. The fibres have a mean diameter of 3 μm and an aspect ratio of 100-200. The fibres are arranged in a pad-like preform (incorporating a silica binder), with most of the fibres oriented in one plane, which is the plane of the preform. Fibre volume fraction of the composites ranged between 7% and 23%. Specimens with zero volume fraction were also tested. The composites were fabricated by the squeeze infiltration method [14], using a final pressure of 30-32 MPa. The matrix grains in the specimens were columnar (about 0.5 mm wide and several mm long), with the long axis of the grains perpendicular to the loading axis of the specimens (and the plane of the preform). Cylindrical specimens were used and they were cut from the plane of the preform. Specimen gauge length and diameter were 20 mm and 8 mm, respectively.

2.2. Monotonic experiments

Monotonic tests at room temperature were performed in an Instron 1175 screw-driven machine with a 100 kN load cell. Clip-on extensometers were used to measure the extension. The crosshead speed was 0.2 mm/min, giving a strain rate of about $2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Monotonic tests at 77 K were performed in an Instron 1341 servo-hydraulic fatigue machine. A temperature of 77 K was obtained by immersing the grips, with specimens and extensometer, in a bath of liquid nitrogen. The strain rate in the low temperature tests was about $6 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$.

The method used to estimate the thermal stress was to measure the stress difference, $\Delta\sigma^{\text{Th}}$, between the tensile and compressive flow curves. This is equivalent to twice the value of the thermal stress [11]. For each fibre volume fraction, at least one specimen was tested in tension and another in compression (additional tests showed that reproducibility of the flow curves was very good). The two curves thus obtained were then superimposed, with the compressive stress and strain both inverted. Examples of the curves at room temperature and 77 K are shown in figures 1a and 1b.

For the composites, the flow in tension and compression is markedly different at low strains, but beyond a strain of about 0.1% to 0.2% the flow curves become parallel. The value of the plastic strain at which the stress difference was evaluated was chosen to be 0.25%. The stress difference was measured along an elastic line for which the modulus was calculated using the Eshelby method (e.g. the modulus has a value of 77 GPa for a fibre volume fraction of 7%). The results for the thermal stresses are shown in figure 2.

a)

b)

Figures 1a-b. Examples of experimental flow curves in tension and compression for composites with a fibre volume fraction of 7%, tested at (a) room temperature and (b) 77 K. In the room temperature tests, a small tensile preload was unavoidable in the gripping of the specimens. The zero for both load and extension were set before gripping and were not changed subsequently and hence the compressive curves appear to originate at a non-zero load. In figure 1b it is shown how the thermal stress was estimated.

Figure 2. The initial thermal stress in the composites at room temperature and 77 K, as estimated from the results of the cyclic Bauschinger experiments and the monotonic tests.

- * Monotonic tests at room temperature
- + Monotonic tests at 77 K
- Bauschinger experiments at room temperature
- ⊞ Bauschinger experiments at 77 K

2.3. Bauschinger experiments

Bauschinger experiments at room temperature and 77 K were carried out between preset plastic strain limits on a servo-hydraulic Instron 1341 fatigue machine, with the aid of a plastic strain controller [15]. Hysteresis loops were recorded at increasing values of the plastic strain amplitude for each specimen in the range 0.05% to 0.5% (in all tests, the value of the imposed plastic strain was the same in tension and compression). Three cycles were taken at each plastic strain level, and the second cycle recorded.

The permanent softening in a Bauschinger experiment can be written as

$$\Delta\sigma = |\sigma^f| - |\sigma^r| = 2 \frac{|\langle\sigma_3\rangle_M^P - \langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^P| \mp |\langle\sigma_3\rangle_M^{Th} - \langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^{Th}|}{1 + B} \quad i = 1 \text{ or } 2 \quad (1)$$

with $-/+$ for tension/compression forward [16]. σ^f is the forward flow stress and σ^r the reverse flow stress. $\langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^P$ is the plastic component of the mean stress and $\langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^{Th}$ the thermal stress. B is a constant for a given fibre volume fraction and relates to the elastic component of the mean stress [16]. Equation 1 shows that it is the difference in the mean and thermal stresses between the loading direction (3) and the transverse directions (1 and 2) which gives the contribution to the permanent softening. As the transverse directions, 1 and 2, are not identical in the composite studied here, both have to be taken into account. If $\Delta\sigma^t$ is written for tension forward and $\Delta\sigma^c$ for compression forward, we obtain (see ref. 12 for an explanation of how $\Delta\sigma^t$ and $\Delta\sigma^c$ are evaluated from the hysteresis loops)

$$\Delta\sigma^t = 2 \frac{|\langle\sigma_3\rangle_M^P - \langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^P| - |\langle\sigma_3\rangle_M^{Th} - \langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^{Th}|}{1 + B} \quad i = 1 \text{ or } 2 \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta\sigma^c = 2 \frac{|\langle\sigma_3\rangle_M^P - \langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^P| + |\langle\sigma_3\rangle_M^{Th} - \langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^{Th}|}{1 + B} \quad i = 1 \text{ or } 2 \quad (3)$$

Thus, a knowledge of $\Delta\sigma^t$ and $\Delta\sigma^c$ enables a separation of the mean and thermal stresses

$$\frac{1}{4}(\Delta\sigma^c + \Delta\sigma^t) = 2 \frac{|\langle\sigma_3\rangle_M^P - \langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^P|}{1 + B} \quad i = 1 \text{ or } 2 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{1}{4}(\Delta\sigma^c - \Delta\sigma^t) = \frac{|\langle\sigma_3\rangle_M^{Th} - \langle\sigma_i\rangle_M^{Th}|}{1 + B} \quad i = 1 \text{ or } 2 \quad (5)$$

As the composite is isotropic in the 2-3 plane, the difference between the thermal stress in the 2 and 3 direction is zero. The right hand side of equation 5, with $i=1$, is then expected to represent an upper limit to the thermal stress in an unrelaxed composite.

The hysteresis loops obtained from tests on a given specimen at increasing values of the plastic strain amplitude were analysed to give values of $\Delta\sigma^p$ and $\Delta\sigma^c$. Equation 5 could be used then to obtain the thermal stress and the mean stress terms. An example of the behaviour of the thermal stress derived from the Bauschinger experiments is shown in figure 3. Extrapolation of the thermal stress to zero plastic strain enabled a measurement of the initial thermal stress in the composite to be made. The results for thermal stresses derived from the Bauschinger experiments are shown in figure 2.

3. The thermal stress at room temperature and 77 K

In figure 2, a comparison is made between the thermal stress derived from the monotonic and Bauschinger tests. For all specimens, there is reasonable agreement between the two methods, although at the higher fibre volume fractions, the thermal stress derived from the Bauschinger experiments is slightly higher than that obtained in the monotonic tests. It is not obvious why this occurs, though it is clear that the extrapolation to zero plastic strain used in the derivation of the thermal stress from the cyclic results may introduce a small error. The generally good agreement between the two methods provides support for the separation analysis for the mean and thermal stresses and, in addition, suggests that the separation analysis for the cyclic tests can be used with confidence as a method of monitoring changes in the thermal stress with cycling (see later).

The thermal stress shows a strong dependence on temperature (figure 2). What is surprising, however, is that the thermal stress appears to be roughly independent of fibre volume fraction. The results for all the composites at room temperature are scattered between 6 MPa and 14 MPa, and at 77 K between 15 MPa and 24 MPa. Theoretically, the thermal stress can be expressed by

$$\frac{1}{2}\Delta\sigma^{Th} = \frac{\langle\sigma_3\rangle_M^{Th} - \langle\sigma_1\rangle_M^{Th}}{1 + B} = \frac{\{A(\alpha_M - \alpha_f)\}_3 - \{A(\alpha_M - \alpha_f)\}_1}{1 + B} |\Delta T| \quad (6)$$

where α_M and α_f are the coefficients of thermal expansion of the matrix and fibres, respectively. A is a constant for a given fibre volume fraction and relates to the plastic component of the mean stress, and ΔT is the difference between the "lock-on" temperature and the temperature at which the composite is tested [16]. This expression represents an upper limit to the matrix stress arising from a temperature change of ΔT and does not take relaxation into account. Ignoring relaxation, the thermal stress is expected to increase linearly with fibre volume fraction. For example, for a ΔT of 250 K, the thermal stress is predicted to increase from about 10 MPa at $f=5\%$ to about 32 MPa at $f=15\%$. Hence, the constancy of the thermal stress in these specimens suggests that as the fibre volume fraction increases, the extent of relaxation of the thermal stress increases.

Equation 6 can be used to calculate a derived value of ΔT from the experimental results and this is shown in figure 4 which is based on the monotonic test data. The results suggest that for the room temperature tests, the "lock-on" temperature falls from a value of about 440 K at $f=7\%$ to about 340 K at $f=23\%$. At 77 K, the change is from about 380 K at $f=7\%$ to about 180 K at $f=23\%$. At 77 K, the change is from about 380 K at $f=7\%$ to 180 K at $f=23\%$. The difference between the room temperature and the liquid nitrogen results is much smaller than the difference between room temperature and 77 K which suggests that further relaxation of the thermal stresses occurs for the specimens which were cooled down to 77 K,

Figure 3

Figure 3. Typical behaviour of the thermal stress (as evaluated by equation 5) in a cyclic Bauschinger experiment on a composite tested at room temperature ($f=10\%$). The arrow shows the order in which the loops were recorded.

Figure 4

Figure 4. The temperature drop ΔT for each fibre volume fraction, obtained by combining experimental estimates of the thermal stress (i.e. by using $\Delta\sigma^{Th}$ from the monotonic tests, see figures 1b and 2) and the theoretical prediction of equation 6.

Figure 5. The thermal stress for a specimen which was annealed for 1 hour at 350°C and water quenched before being tested in a cyclic Bauschinger experiment at room temperature. The same procedure of annealing, quenching and testing was then repeated. The arrows show the order in which the loops were recorded and psa stands for plastic strain amplitude.

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|------------------|
| After first anneal and water quench: | □ Increasing psa |
| | ⊠ Decreasing psa |
| After second anneal and water quench: | + Increasing psa |
| | * Decreasing psa |

and that this relaxation increases with fibre volume fraction. It seems possible that plastic deformation in the matrix during cooling leads to relief of the thermal stresses, and that the extent of this plastic deformation increases with increasing fibre volume fraction.

4. Recovery of thermal stresses

The reduction of the thermal stress with repeated cycling shown in figure 3 is typical of composites tested at room temperature. Composites tested at 77 K show a much smaller rate of reduction of the thermal stress with cycling. Extensive cycling at room temperature can reduce the thermal stress significantly, but cannot eliminate it completely.

The purpose of the experiment described here was to check whether small amounts of cumulative plastic strain, of the type produced in these cyclic Bauschinger experiments, causes irreversible damage to the specimen, such as voiding, fibre/matrix debonding etc. A specimen was annealed for 1 hour at 350°C and water quenched. Immediately after the quench, Bauschinger experiments were carried out at room temperature. The plastic strain amplitude was increased in steps from 0.05% to 0.38% and then reduced to 0.05% (figure 5). After this, the specimen was annealed and water quenched for a second time, and then mechanically tested using the same procedure as before, with very slightly different plastic strain amplitude values. The results of this experiment are given in figure 5. After the first anneal and water quench, the thermal stress is reduced from about 11 MPa to about 6 MPa during the testing, and remains roughly constant. After the second heat treatment and quench, the initial value of the thermal stress was recovered and the behaviour of the thermal stress is almost identical to the behaviour after the first heat treatment. This demonstrates that the reduction in the thermal stress caused by the cycling can be reversed by annealing and quenching. Hence, the reduction is not caused by irreversible damage in the form of voiding, fibre/matrix debonding, etc.

5. Conclusions

1. The thermal stress in the matrix of metal matrix composites can be measured by comparing monotonic flow curves in tension and compression or by analysing the results of cyclic Bauschinger experiments. The latter method allows changes in the thermal stress to be monitored, which is useful in composites which show a marked relaxation of thermal stresses with cycling.

2. The reduction in the thermal stress with cycling, at least for small cumulative plastic strains and small plastic strain amplitudes, is not caused by irreversible damage such as voiding or fibre/matrix debonding. The thermal stress can be restored to its initial magnitude by annealing and quenching the specimen.

Acknowledgements

It is a pleasure to thank Professor L.M. Brown and Dr. O.B. Pedersen for discussions during the course of this work and Mr. A. Robinson for help with designing a plastic strain controller. BJ would like to thank the British ambassador in Iceland and the Foreign and Commonwealth office for financial support during this work. BJ is also grateful to Minningarsjodur Helgu Jonsdottur og Sigurlida Kristjanssonar, University of Iceland, for additional financial assistance.

References

1. Brown, L.M., Stobbs, W.M., The work-hardening of copper-silica I. A model based on internal stresses, with no plastic relaxation, *Phil. Mag.*, 23, pp. 1185-1199, 1971.
2. Atkinson, J.D., Brown, L.M., Stobbs, W.M., The work-hardening of copper-silica IV. The Bauschinger effect and plastic relaxation, *Phil. Mag.*, 30, pp. 1247-1280, 1974.
3. Brown, L.M., Clarke, D.R., Work hardening due to internal stresses in composite materials, *Acta Metall.*, 23, No. 7, pp. 821-830, 1975.
4. Brown, L.M., Clarke, D.R., The work hardening of fibrous composites with particular reference to the copper-tungsten system, *Acta Metall.*, 25, pp. 563-570, 1977.
5. Lilholt, H., Hardening in two-phase materials I. Strength contributions in fibre-reinforced copper-tungsten, *Acta Metall.*, 25, pp. 571-585, 1977.
6. Pedersen, O.B., Thermoelasticity and plasticity of composite materials, In: Miller, K.J., et al., eds, *Mechanical behaviour of materials, proceedings of the third international conference (ICM-3)*, Cambridge, England, Pergamon press, pp. 263-273, 1979.
7. Pedersen, O.B., Thermoelasticity and plasticity of composites I. Mean field theory., *Acta Metall.*, 31, No. 11, pp. 1795-1808, 1983.
8. Pedersen, O.B., Thermoelasticity and plasticity of composites II. A model system., *Acta Metall. Mater.*, 38, No. 7, pp. 1201-1219, 1990.
9. Cheskis, H.P., Heckel, R.W., Deformation behaviour of continuous-fibre metal-matrix composite materials, *Metallurgical Transactions*, 1, pp. 1931-1942, 1970.
10. Withers, P.J., Juul Jensen, D., Lilholt, H., Stobbs, W.M., The evaluation of internal stresses in a short fibre metal matrix composite by neutron diffraction., In: Matthews, F.L., et al. eds., *proceedings of ICCM 6/ECCM 2*, 20-24 july, 1987, London, Elsevier, pp. 2.255-2.264, 1987.
11. Arsenault, R.J., Taya, M., Thermal residual stress in metal matrix composite., *Acta Metall.*, 35, No. 3, pp. 651-659, 1987.
12. Johannesson, B., Ogin, S.L., Tsakirooulos, P., Internal stresses and the cyclic deformation of a discontinuous fibre reinforced aluminium composite., In: Hansen, N., et al. eds., *Metal Matrix Composites - Processing, Microstructure and Properties*, Proceedings of the 12th Risø international symposium on materials science, 2-6 sept., 1991, Risø National Laboratory, Denmark, pp. 411-416, 1991.
13. Data Sheet, ICI, Saffil alumina fibre. Applications in metal matrix composites. ICI, Mond division, Runcorn, Cheshire, UK, 1982.
14. Clyne, T.W., Bader, M.G., Cappleman, G.R., Hubert, P.A., The use of δ -alumina fibre for metal matrix composites., *Journal of Materials Science*, 20, pp. 85-96, 1985.
15. Wilson, C.J., Robinson, A., Control of plastic extension in fatigue tests., *Journal of Physics E, Scientific instruments*, 10, pp. 129-132, 1977.
16. Withers, P.J., Stobbs, W.M., Pedersen, O.B., The application of the Eshelby method of internal stress determination to short fibre metal matrix composites., *Acta Metall.*, 37, No. 11, pp. 3061-3084, 1989.